

Design of a Hybrid Architecture for P2P Network

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Abstract— Free rider detection plays a very important role in the stability of a P2P network. Free riders tend to utilize the benefits from the network by downloading files from it without giving back to the network. This has adverse effect on the quality and lifetime of the whole network. Various approaches have been developed for mitigating free-riding; most of them are suffering from some limitations with regard to having correctly represented behavior at the peers and preventing the distribution of fake or duplicate files. To overcome these shortcomings, this work proposes a dynamically assigned grace period and a content scanning mechanism to prevent free riders and stop peers from uploading repeated and fake files in the network. Prototype of the system was implemented with C# programming language and tested on a simulated network. The result showed that the system achieved a free rider detection rate of up to 60%, a duplicate file detection rate of 66%, and a fake file detection rate of 33% at a network size of 2000 peers. These results reflect the efficiency of the hybrid architecture in solving significant questions of free riding and authenticity of content for the more stable and secure development of the P2P environment.

Keywords— Hybrid Architecture, Peer-to-Peer(P2P) Network, Dynamic grace period, Content Scanning Mechanism.

I. INTRODUCTION

The application and the implementation of a Hybrid Architecture in peer-to-peer networks are expected solutions to generally shared problems such as free riding that is, users consuming resources without contributing anything in return bringing down network performance and reliability in general [23]. This architecture will combine both P2P and client-server elements to leverage the strengths of each while ensuring generalized efficiency of resource distribution for robustness in general networks [24].

The hybrid architecture prototype was introduced during the conference proceedings with the purpose of mitigating free riding in P2P networks. This prototype makes use of a dynamic grace period allocation mechanism along with a content scanning system for ensuring fair resource sharing with no repeated file uploads. The framework provided a theoretical one, with initial steps for the implementation to validate the feasibility of the proposed mechanisms relying on conceptual designs and basic functionality testing [37]. Based on this prototype, this work further extends those efforts by implementing the proposed hybrid architecture, in C#, as a full-scale simulation using dynamic grace periods

and content scanning mechanisms in a simulated environment. In this respect, performance metrics such as free rider detection rate, duplicate file detection rate, and fake file detection rate are compared against differing network sizes. This work considers the architecture's comprehensiveness for scalability and effectiveness in ensuring resource sharing, file integrity, and stability of the overall network as a way to complement the limitations identified in the earlier work. It proposes dynamic grace period allocation with a content scanning mechanism for encouraging resource sharing to maintain stability, enhancing quality within the network while preserving file integrity.

Various methods are implemented for the Hybrid Architecture, such as prioritization of peers based on their bandwidth and position of playbacks to enable efficient VoD video streaming. This methodology keeps the users with high bandwidth closer to the media sources to ensure smooth streaming services for all users [23]. Game-theoretic incentives for participation integrated into the platform discourage free riding while rewarding cooperative peers and penalizing those that do not contribute to the network resources [24]. The hybrid model further integrates a community management layer aimed at managing transactions by boosting security and building trust within the network [25]. Despite these benefits, effective peer-to-peer control involves addressing the dynamic behaviour of network users and managing resource allocation efficiently. Ensuring seamless cooperation among peers without central oversight can be challenging, as the system must account for diverse user behaviours, network fluctuations, and high churn rates [24]. Moreover, traditional approaches may struggle to scale effectively as networks grow, necessitating hybrid models that balance decentralization with centralized elements to maintain performance and reliability [23].

In order to deal with such issues, the improved Hybrid Architecture developed in this research work is based on two mechanisms: dynamic grace period and content scanning mechanism. Dynamic grace period mechanisms award or remove privileges according to the activity of the peers; participation is rewarded by granting more access, and free-riding is penalized by isolating those who do not contribute their resources. The content scanning mechanism will avoid both uploading repeated/fake files and maintain file integrity within the network. The research is organised in the following

manner Section 1.0 provides an introduction and background on P2P networks and hybrid architectures. Section 2.0 embarks on reviewing existing works on techniques for mitigating free-riding and enhancing peer interactions. Section 3.0 discusses the methods used in implementing the hybrid model. Section 4.0 presents the results obtained and their discussions. Section 5 presents the prototype development. Section 6 gives the conclusion of the research work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The authors in [5] developed a point-system where peers are encouraged to spend to earn points and those points can only be spent on leeching implying that contributing peers get better download speed while free-riders ones slow down. [6] proposed a credit-based model with free-riders and termed this group condition as Grace period assigning those peers who do not submit computing resources within the deadline.[20] explores whether monetary incentives can attract peers to participate in peer-to-peer (P2P) content delivery systems.

[1] employed the game theory approach with Ayo game model, which greatly mitigated free-riders in semi-decentralized networks. [8] brings about an idea that has to do with the sustenance of the togetherness of individuals that are not related using a game theory side of view. [14] In his study, presented a difference between groups of people limited to playing pure strategies and groups of people given the privilege to play mixed strategies in a one-shot symmetric PD laboratory experiment. [9] in his study, he uses a centrality relationship incentive mechanism. [13] presented an incentive mechanism for P2P file sharing based on social network and game theory. [21] introduces a dynamic and incomplete game model to analyze peer interactions and proposes a co-opetition framework to control free riding. The study uses simulations to test the co-opetition framework under various environments.

[11] proposed a balanced peer-to-peer content delivery. In his work, two methods were presented to ensure fair p2p content delivery, which are EqualDownload, and EqualStream with the aid of blockchain for p2p downloading and p2p streaming cases. [10] in his brings about an idea for distributed P2P where a cryptocurrency such as Bitcoin was used to promote user for cooperation such that users that helps with delivery that results in a success is rewarded. [15] presented a blockchain-based incentive mechanism for sharing cyber threat intelligence. [16] presented a reward mechanism for blockchains using evolutionary game theory. [17] proposed security frame does not need any central server and it not prone to attacks like RTI and Sybil attacks.

[3] introduced a decentralized reputation system for P2P-networks through the implementation blockchain technology to help satisfy demand, as it increases peer contributions and free-riding. To make them fair [22] explored the improvements in fairness of decentralized storage networks by considering bandwidth incentives through simulation and obtained a more equitable distribution of rewards among peers [4] from a game theoretical perspective, proposes a system that uses a reputation-based approach to allocate resources in P2P system. This method/idea makes sure that peers want are as a result of their shared capacity. [12] proposes a Simplified Biased Contribution Index (SBCI) as

an incentive mechanism to balance resource sharing in peer-to-peer (P2P) networks. Unlike previous methods, SBCI does not require iterative calculations or strict clock synchronization, making it more efficient and easier to implement. [18] proposes an incentive-based security model for Peer-to-Peer (P2P) networks to ensure fairness. Prevent free riders by making leechers contribute as much as they download. Protect seeders by reducing their workload and ensuring they are treated fairly. Secure communication using cryptographic methods like RSA to prevent spying.

[7] in his work, utilizes a sharing idea that is ratio based for distributing resources in P2P networks and sharing files are done using BitTorrent protocol. One of the strengths of this study is that it not susceptible to sybil attack and gangs up attack by group peers as it was introduced majorly to foster cooperation amidst peers, bring about fairness to downloaders and prevent free riders and whitewashing attacks. [2] bring about a idea that is inspired by a Market setting to curb free-riding behaviour a P2P network fog computing to be precise. in his study proposed the AFMIA that takes into consideration resources as goods that have varied worth based on the extent of demand and supply. [19] presented a KeyPIn scheme combines Key-based, Participation-based, and Incentive-based mechanisms to encourage resource sharing and participation in the cloud. It uses game theory to create incentives for users to contribute resources, while limiting access for free riders. Simulation results demonstrate that the KeyPIn scheme effectively reduces the presence of free riders in the distributed cloud, ensuring more equitable resource distribution and improved overall system performance.

Various approaches also have been suggested that aimed at enhancing the performance and security of P2P systems by better mitigation of free-riding, resource management, and integrity of content. A widely used mechanism includes the application of distributed incentive mechanisms that guide the peers with higher upload bandwidth closer to the sources by optimizing VoD streaming efficiency and reducing the cases of buffering [23]. This mechanism indeed works effectively in resource distribution management, enhancing QoS; however, the system might be complex to implement and may not scale well for larger networks [23]. Another way this concern is being taken on board is by using a reputation-driven algorithm, which calculates the reputation of peers based on their behavioural considerations. Reputation-based methods use game-theoretic approaches where cooperating peers are rewarded while free riders are penalized to ensure network stability [25]. However, the complexity in the computation of reputation and the resulting additional communication overhead may affect scalability [24].

Other architectures represent hybrid systems that realize a combination of both P2P and client-server models. In fact, these hybrid architectures retain the typical scalability associated with P2P systems but can maintain some degree of centralized control. An example of such hybrid P2P overlays is the use of semantic web technologies, which extend resource discovery and knowledge-sharing capabilities by means of metadata and ontologies [25]. This semantic layer enhances efficiency in locating resources from the point of view of access and managing them, but it adds performance overhead at the cost of possibly introducing a number of interoperability challenges in heterogeneous systems [25].

Another hybrid model is the G-CP2P Architecture, which uses a super-peer mechanism for content distribution and location-aware peer selection, effectively managing latency and enhancing scalability through content distribution management among the peers [26]. While efficient, this system depends largely on super-peer availability, which tends to become a bottleneck for the performance of such a system [26].

Security and trust have also been addressed using layered architectures that integrate both fully decentralized and fully centralized elements. A hybrid P2P system that adopts PKI working with a trust management algorithm enhances security and reliability in transactions, effectively decentralizing sharing at higher layers [27]. While such systems increase scalability and can be more secure, the added centralizing elements reduce some of the advantages of full decentralization [27]. Similarly, hybrid architectures with DHT and Voronoi diagrams for data distribution provide a scaling solution for MMGs, where consistency in game state is particularly essential [28]. However, the implementation of this hybrid model faces issues of latency and security problems, especially when real-time applications are involved [28].

Other topics that have also received attention are related to the application of game theory in the context of P2P networks, used for managing interactions among altruists and free riders. Game-theoretic algorithms are used to develop a co-opetition framework that incentivizes resource sharing and maintains balanced and fair resource distribution [29]. These game-theory-based models, however, have assumptions about user behaviour through which scalability may be hard to achieve in larger and more heterogeneous P2P systems, even though they work effectively in smaller-scale networks [29]. A recent promising strategy relates to the use of blockchain technology in an attempt to provide hybrid CDN-P2P architectures with storage and recording mechanisms for secure and transparent transactions, together with zero-knowledge proofs (zk-SNARKs) to protect the privacy of the users while further improving security and scalability [30]. The implementation of blockchains and zk-SNARKs is nevertheless complex and may introduce some performance overhead; moreover, their novelty today also introduces barriers to adoption [30]. Another example is ALIVE, which uses P2P and CDN resources in a hybrid framework. It allows for the best scalability with cost efficiency. With the approach using NFV, edge computing dynamically orchestrates the resources for improving user experience; this indeed relies heavily on the availability and reliability of the P2P resources [31].

In addition, ABR algorithms were studied over hybrid CDN/P2P networks for video delivery, dynamically adapting the quality of the content to network conditions. This increases the perceived quality of service for the customers [32]. Enhanced ABR algorithms cope with variable network conditions to maintain QoS, although confirmation of their applicability in real-world scenarios is required [32]. Moreover, distributed incentive mechanisms that organize peers due to their upload bandwidth and playback point have been promising for VoD streaming. It allows smooth playback and resilience against dynamic network changes

[33]. However, this method relies upon the willingness of peers and thus may restrict the reliability of the method [33].

Hybrid architecture service discovery and load balancing algorithms have shown to lessen infrastructure costs and enhance the flexibility of the P2P-based cloud computing model [34]. While the peer-to-peer structure allows clients to be both providers and consumers, there is a host of issues on aspects such as reliability and data security in a decentralized system, and challenges remain significant [34]. Machine learning models find themselves applied to adaptive peer selection in hybrid CDN-P2P systems as well, with improvements in data throughput and reductions in messaging delay being considered substantial [35]. Yet, the complexity and computational overhead of those systems may pose a challenge to scalability over large networks [35].

Again, hybrid P2P architectures for transaction management combine centralization with decentralized peer behaviour and address security and trust through layered authentication and non-repudiation protocols as well as community management layers [36]. This architecture has shown promise in improving the reliability and scalability of transactions within P2P systems. Balancing centralization and decentralization, however, remains a significant challenge [36].

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper presents the design of a hybrid peer-to-peer system in order to alleviate the problem of free riding and avoid fake and duplicate files within a network. It integrates a Dynamic Grace Period approach and a Content Scanning Mechanism into what is here referred to as the Improved Hybrid P2P Architecture. System performance was benchmarked against a Normal Hybrid P2P architecture using simulations implemented as a desktop application in C#. The data management in the simulation was done by using in-memory structures, and the main one used is the DataGrid View. It did not use any external databases. The algorithm governing the simulation process is detailed in Algorithm 1, and the architecture of the Improved Hybrid P2P system is depicted in Fig. 1.

A. Simulation Setup and Peer Activities

A network containing from 100 to 2,000 peers was simulated, then subjected to random file upload and download processes. Synthetic data for files and peer interactions were generated dynamically during the simulation. Each peer was uniquely identified by its upload and download counts, as well as a status indicating whether it was a free rider or a contributing peer. The metadata of the files, the timestamp of the uploads, and the peer statuses were stored and updated in an application based on DataGrid View, forming a lightweight, self-contained database model for this simulation. Fig. 1 shows the interface used to perform the simulation.

Fig. 1: Interface used to perform the simulation

B. Algorithm for Simulation Workflow

ALGORITHM 1 SIMULATION WORKFLOW

```

START
  Initialize Simulation
  Input: Total peers (P), Simulation cycles (C)
  Set all peers to default statuses (non-free riders)
  compute_unique_value
  extract_key_features
  store in server records
  Simulation Loop (for each cycle)
  Randomly assign actions (Upload, Download, Idle) to peers
  For uploads:
    Compute file hash and verify for duplicates or fakes (Improved Hybrid)
    Record successful uploads and update peer status
  For downloads:
    Check peer's free-rider status (Improved Hybrid)
    Allow or deny download accordingly
  Update peer statuses
  Apply the dynamic grace period mechanism for free riders
  Metrics Collection
  Update detection rates for free riders, duplicates, and fake files
  Stop Simulation
  When all cycles are completed or predefined conditions are met
  Output Results
  Display performance metrics for both architectures
End
    
```

ALGORITHM 1: CONTENT SCANNING MECHANISM (FILE UPLOAD)

```

START
  If first_time_upload:
    allow_upload
    scan_file
    compute_unique_value
    extract_key_features
    store in server records
  else:
    scan_file
    compare_with_previous_upload
  If unique:
    allow_upload
    store_in_server_records
  else if rare_file:
    
```

```

    allow_upload
  else:
    deny_upload
    
```

End

ALGORITHM 2: CONTENT SCANNING MECHANISM (FILE DOWNLOAD)

```

START
  If file request
    connect_requesting_peer_with_sending_peer
    If download_successful:
      requesting_peer_send_status_and_file_to_server
      server_scan_file
      verify_key_features
      update_records
    else:
      do_nothing
  End
    
```

This algorithm ensures the integrity and authenticity of files shared within the network by implementing a robust content verification process. The development process involves creating a system that scans files before they are uploaded to the centralized server. Unique values and key features are extracted from the scanned files and stored in the server records. The algorithm compares new files with previously uploaded ones to determine if they are duplicates or unique.

Steps and procedures

Step 1: If it is the first time a peer is trying to make a file available for download:

- i. The peer is allowed to upload the file to the server.
- ii. The server scans the file, computes a unique value, extracts key features, and stores this information along with the peer's details.

Step 2: If the peer has previously uploaded files:

- i. The server scans the new file and compares its unique value with previously uploaded files.

- ii. If the file is unique, it is allowed for upload; if it is a duplicate, the upload is denied unless the file is marked as rare by the server.

Step 3: When a peer requests a file, the server facilitates a connection between the requesting peer and the sending peer.

Step 4: Upon successful download, the requesting peer sends a status and the downloaded file back to the server.

Step 5: The server scans the downloaded file to verify the key features and updates the records accordingly.

C. Hybrid P2P Architectures

Normal Hybrid P2P Architecture

The Normal Hybrid P2P architecture as shown in Fig. 3 operates without dynamic adjustments or content verification mechanisms:

- i. Peer activities (upload, download, idle) are executed randomly.
- ii. There is no enforcement of a grace period or scanning for duplicates and fake files.

Improved Hybrid P2P Architecture

The Improved Hybrid P2P architecture as shown in Fig. 2 integrates two novel mechanisms:

- a) Dynamic Grace Period:
 - i. Peers with a download-upload difference > 10 are assigned a dynamically calculated grace period.
 - ii. If peers upload files before the grace period expires, a new grace period starts dynamically.
 - iii. Failure to upload within the grace period marks the peer as a free rider, disabling their download privileges.
- b) Content Scanning Mechanism:
 - i. Each uploaded file is scanned for uniqueness and fake content.
 - ii. Unique hash values and key features are computed for each file. Duplicate or fake files are flagged and rejected, except for rare or unique files, which bypass duplicate checks.

Fig. 2. Improved Hybrid Architecture (Akinboro et al., 2024)

Fig. 3. Normal Hybrid P2P Architecture (Reza, 2009)

The IHADGPCSM (Improved Hybrid Architecture with Dynamic Grace Period and Content Scanning Mechanism) as shown in Fig. 3 addresses free riding in hybrid P2P networks by dynamically assigning grace periods based on a download popularity **score** and using a content scanning mechanism to ensure file uniqueness and integrity. The index server facilitates connections between uploading peers (UPs) and requesting peers (RPs). It scans files uploaded by UPs to verify their uniqueness, denying uploads if the file already exists unless it is classified as "rare." It also maintains records of file features, such as unique values and extracted attributes, along with peer interaction data for verification purposes. For downloads, the server verifies files sent by RPs by comparing their extracted features with stored records, ensuring integrity.

The dynamic grace period allocation mechanism initially allows peers to download up to 10 files without restrictions. Once this limit is reached, a grace period is calculated, requiring the peer to upload at least one file to regain download privileges. The grace period dynamically adjusts based on the peer's updated download popularity score, which is calculated using upload and download scores. Peers are allowed to upload unique files freely, while repeated files are only accepted if classified as "rare." The content scanning

mechanism ensures that files uploaded by UPs are scanned for uniqueness, and if found to be duplicates, the upload request is denied. RPs' downloaded files are sent back to the server for verification, and only verified files are recorded, with corresponding scores assigned to both the UP and RP. Peers whose uploads exceed or equal their downloads can interact freely with the system. However, if downloads surpass uploads, the calculated grace period activates, requiring the peer to upload a file before further downloads are allowed. This system ensures balanced peer contributions, discourages free riding, and promotes only unique and verified files within the network.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation was performed with varying numbers of peers (100, 500, 1000, 1500, and 2000) to evaluate the performance of both the Normal Hybrid P2P Architecture and the Improved Hybrid P2P Architecture as shown in Fig 4. The results focus on the Free Rider Detection Rate, Duplicate File Detection Rate, and Fake File Detection Rate. Table I summarizes the performance metrics across the two architectures.

Fig. 4. Result of the simulation with 2000 peers

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE METRICS COMPARISON

Peers	Architecture	Free Rider Detection Rate (%)	Duplicate File Detection Rate (%)	Fake File Detection Rate (%)
100	Normal Hybrid P2P	24%	N/A	N/A
	Improved Hybrid P2P	36%	33%	16%
500	Normal Hybrid P2P	28%	N/A	N/A
	Improved Hybrid P2P	41%	40%	20%
1000	Normal Hybrid P2P	32%	N/A	N/A
	Improved Hybrid P2P	48%	60%	22%
1500	Normal Hybrid P2P	36%	N/A	N/A
	Improved Hybrid P2P	53%	60%	20%
2000	Normal Hybrid P2P	40%	N/A	N/A
	Improved Hybrid P2P	60%	66%	33%

Table I compares the performance of the Normal Hybrid P2P and Improved Hybrid P2P architectures in detecting free riders, duplicate files, and fake files. Simulations were conducted with varying numbers of peers (100, 500, 1000, 1500, and 2000). In terms of free rider detection rate, the Improved Hybrid P2P consistently outperforms the Normal Hybrid P2P in detecting free riders across all peer counts. For 100 peers, the Normal Hybrid P2P detected 24% of free riders, while the Improved Hybrid P2P achieved a detection rate of 36%. As the number of peers increased to 2000, the free rider detection rate for the Normal Hybrid P2P rose to 40%, while the Improved Hybrid P2P reached 60%. In terms of duplicate file detection rate, the Normal Hybrid P2P does not include a mechanism for detecting duplicate files, leaving

its detection rate as N/A across all peer counts. While the Improved Hybrid P2P demonstrates strong duplicate file detection, starting at 33% with 100 peers and increasing to 66% with 2000 peers, showing a scalable improvement with the number of peers. In terms of fake file detection rate, the Normal Hybrid P2P lacks the ability to detect fake files, resulting in N/A for this metric. While the Improved Hybrid P2P begins with a fake file detection rate of 16% at 100 peers, reaching 33% with 2000 peers. This indicates a steady increase in its ability to identify fake files as the system scales.

Fig. 5. Free Rider Detection Rate

Fig. 6. Duplicate File Detection Rate

Fig. 7. Fake File Detection Rate

V. PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

Following the results, this section discusses the design and implementation of the prototype. The prototype was developed using the C# programming language which is a simple, modern, general-purpose object-oriented

programming language that provide server-side and client-side support for developing enterprise and multi-tier applications, incorporating two core mechanisms: dynamic grace period allocation and content scanning.

The UML class diagram as shown in Fig. 8 outlines the key system components, such as Peers, Files, Index Server, and GracePeriodAllocator, showing how they interact to manage file sharing and grace period allocation based on peer activities. The entity relation diagram as shown in Fig. 9 displays how data entities like Peers, Files, Requests, and the Index Server are connected, illustrating the relationships within the database that track uploaded and downloaded files. The sequence diagram as shown in Fig. 10 shows the sequence of actions when a requesting peer asking for a file, with the index server verifying the availability, facilitating the connection with the uploading peer, and monitoring the interaction via the grace period allocator. Fig. 11 shows the Database information on files uploaded by peers to the system While Fig. 12 shows the simulator home screen interface.

Fig. 8: UML Class diagram for the prototype

Fig. 9. Entity relationship diagram for the prototype

Fig. 10: Interactions among the components

FileID	FileName	Hash	UploadedBy	UploadDate
1	File1.txt	a4488703f13c09b77140e23a9782cf18d27e0c44102f1	1	2024-10-09 20:47:47.540
2	File2.txt	a70e3e4ef1c6655504e04445605c3a133b9617524a	2	2024-10-09 20:48:19.887
3	File3.txt	4ea3e5c0290c7c5c0a9a8d8f6118a540a066753407af5	3	2024-10-09 20:49:07.280
4	File4.txt	a7598e2ec0272c308a9e9f7110a85c56e6b3a6b23d	4	2024-10-09 20:49:36.027
5	File5.txt	3189979598414270b5ca1551b47457659a7babc4234a0b	5	2024-10-09 20:50:16.490
6	File6.txt	e917b1817e05c448987047894e970ec8040381c5330cb	6	2024-10-09 20:50:52.283
7	File7.txt	31522844e478a03a9f7992e16870c2016c4b0c8e65	7	2024-10-09 20:51:22.413
8	File8.txt	d4ee039f6b8f593e630893242624687d9471e79ecb	8	2024-10-09 20:51:47.803
9	File9.txt	0a990100e0c1a1e4d25509b1351816a9f4b1c38a13e	9	2024-10-09 20:52:12.743
10	File10.txt	9956c4f6e0e54e56c6e408c1ba185e222ba42c56c8d	10	2024-10-09 20:52:59.427
11	File11.txt	6847290903a934d9a4b0705178d084423409310a027	1	2024-10-09 20:53:47.927
12	File12.txt	7708726c4045556295292826d7b3750a227c10f6d8f03d	1	2024-10-09 20:53:55.640
13	File13.txt	c29e24659a72067867d18f6e3108390815678c10e68	1	2024-10-09 21:13:57.960
14	File14.txt	618021505c034e45c633afed8b8c4490ead00a7b30722	1	2024-10-09 21:44:04.837
15	File15.txt	ee7706a0211108196164a639a0a4084939c0b187e10572	1	2024-10-09 21:44:23.587
16	File16.txt	9255a4db30f06e6e6e6ed6d11e7e1e4101410a8896d	2	2024-10-09 21:48:48.723
17	File17.txt	58115586014318c50148c08f3c84926661b5096197b10678	2	2024-10-09 21:57:11.913
18	File18.txt	69b47c3ac5e6795934347c01b1622c43fca30aee11546ed	2	2024-10-09 22:11:37.507
19	File19.txt	48738d7eac03460990f9309c1a0a539e409046c3a6f	1	2024-10-09 22:42:52.453
20	File20.txt	30506e0e000094013409e7a0b40305c0c4e603301	2	2024-10-09 22:48:18.113
21	File21.txt	37c45847c5b4c1c544e0c3b5af8201c1629730c8e7e1e7	2	2024-10-11 01:15:29.953
22	File22.txt	c2113001e48e0e64991160a0e656e769333a8f67e7d3d7	2	2024-10-11 01:17:00.213
23	File23.txt	8928413ac48f820ba3e9e42e652c7088ab3a8f4e6e29fd	2	2024-10-11 01:17:47.497
24	File24.txt	3189979598414270b5ca1551b47457659a7babc4234a0b	2	2024-10-14 01:54:03.603

Fig. 11: Database information on files uploaded by peers to the system

Fig. 12: Simulator home screen interface

VI. EVALUATION METRICS

The performance of the prototype was evaluated using the following metrics:

- i. Free Rider Detection Rate: The percentage of peers correctly identified as free riders who meet the free-riding criteria.
- ii. Duplicate File Detection Rate: The percentage of duplicate files accurately identified and blocked.
- iii. Fake File Detection Rate: The percentage of fake files correctly detected and rejected.

A. Free Rider Detection Rate (FRDR)

The percentage of peers correctly identified as free riders, calculated using the formula:

$$FRDR = \left(\frac{\text{Number of free riders correctly detected}}{\text{Total number of actual free riders}} \right) \times 100$$

B. Duplicate File Detection Rate (DFDR)

The accuracy of identifying and blocking duplicate files is measured as:

$$DFDR = \left(\frac{\text{Number of duplicate files detected}}{\text{Total number of duplicate files uploaded}} \right) \times 100$$

C. Fake File Detection Rate (FFDR)

The system's ability to identify fake files is determined using:

$$FFDR = \left(\frac{\text{Number of fake files detected}}{\text{Total number of fake files uploaded}} \right) \times 100$$

The application was implemented using C# for desktop application development, DataGrid View to simulate a lightweight database system for peer activities and file metadata and randomized peer behaviour to emulate realistic P2P network activities.

VII. CONCLUSION

The Improved Hybrid P2P system designed and analyzed in this research effectively mitigates free riding and improves the detection of duplicate and fake files in peer-to-peer networks. Accurately detecting free riders is crucial for ensuring fair resource allocation and maintaining the network's efficiency. Similarly, identifying duplicate and fake files enhances the reliability and integrity of shared content, which is essential for user trust and system performance. This approach can be extended to other computing areas, such as content distribution, network security, and distributed resource management. As demonstrated, the Improved Hybrid P2P system leverages dynamic grace period approach and content scanning mechanism to address key challenges in peer-to-peer networks, outperforming traditional systems and paving the way for more robust and reliable hybrid architectures.

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